

Item	Differences in Ratings (Diff = Douban rating - Goodreads rating, out of 5)	Differences in Numbers of Ratings Received (Diff = Douban num of rating - Goodreads num of ratings)	Divergences of the Distributions of the 1-to-5-Star Ratings (Measured by K-L Divergence)
Min	-0.290	-4,908,789	0.010
Max	0.850	620,027	6.837
Mean	0.262	-196,121	0.252
Std	0.218	683,542	0.635

Table 2. Goodreads and Douban's Differences in (1) Overall Ratings; (2) Numbers of Ratings; and (3) Distributions of Ratings

In addition, we collected and analysed the user-generated ratings and numbers of ratings on both platforms. We measured the differences in parallel ratings, numbers of ratings received per book, and the distributions of the 1-to-5-star ratings for the same books (only the most rated edition/copy) across platforms. Table 2 provides our preliminary findings, as is shown in Table 2. For instance, Table 2 Column 3 shows that on average, each classic receives 196,121 more ratings on Goodreads than on Douban.

Currently, we are further comparing the quantitative and qualitative features of these Goodreads and Douban classics to reveal more differences across the platforms and further understand their implications for ongoing research. While this case study based on Goodreads and Douban makes a unique contribution to the existing cross-cultural analysis of user-generated book reviews, we look forward to expanding our cross-cultural comparisons to other readerships and platforms through collaboration.

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